

Novafert

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D3.4 – Selection of Indicators and monitoring the action plan

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Abbreviations

APRL- Agronomic Performance Readiness level

DoA – Description of the Action (in the NOVAFERT Grant Agreement)

EC – European Commission

EU – European Union

FPR- Fertilising Product Regulation

GAP – General Action Plan

K- Potassium

LFA – Logical Framework Approach

MRL- Market and investment readiness level

N- Nitrogen

NUE- Nutrient Use Efficiency

P- Phosphorus

PEST – Political, Economic, Social and Technological

PFC- Product Function Category

RSAP – Region Specific Action Plan

RSAPs – Region Specific Action Plans

RWGs – Regional Working Groups

S- Sulfur

SRL- Sustainability Readiness Level

SWOT – Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats

TRL- Technology Readiness Level

WP – Work Package

Executive Summary

The NOVAFERT project aims to accelerate the adoption of sustainable, alternative fertilization technologies across Europe, contributing to a circular economy by enhancing nutrient recovery and reducing dependency on conventional fertilisers. This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the progress focusing on the development of Regional Specific Action Plans (RSAPs) and a dashboard with performance indicators for five priority technologies.

The RSAPs have been evaluated through a structured monitoring process that assesses progress across key areas such as legal frameworks, political willingness, research and development, financial incentives, and public acceptance. By tracking regional advancements and identifying barriers, the project ensures that local strategies are tailored to specific socio-economic and environmental contexts, ultimately driving the widespread adoption of alternative fertilisers.

A key innovation of the NOVAFERT project is the creation of a dynamic, multi-dimensional dashboard that monitors and communicates the readiness and performance of the selected technologies. This dashboard integrates key indicators, such as technology readiness, nutrient recovery rates, sustainability, and agronomic performance, providing stakeholders with up-to-date information on the progress and potential impact of each technology. The dashboard serves as a living document, continuously updated to reflect new data, pilot studies, and regulatory changes, ensuring its relevance well beyond the project's completion.

In summary, the executive monitoring of NOVAFERT shows an optimistic picture of progress and potential. The coordinated efforts across different regions have shown that, despite diverse local conditions, everyone shares the same ingredients for success: supportive legislation, smart financial support, relentless innovation, and community engagement. Significant steps have been made on all these fronts. Dozens of new initiatives, from policy reforms to pilot plants, are already up and running, yielding early successes like improved nutrient recycling rates, new products, and growing stakeholder buy-in. At the same time, the work so far has highlighted where more attention is needed. Some policies are still finding their footing, and some technologies await broader acceptance or investment. These gaps are opportunities to cover: they point to where the next rounds of effort should focus. In the coming months and years, regional teams plan to build on this momentum by continuing to share best practices and results with each other. We will likely see more alignment of incentives (for example, new subsidy schemes being refined and launched), more on-the-ground demonstrations to turn sceptics into adopters, and further simplification of rules that currently limit alternative fertilisers. By staying the course - jointly refining policies, funding, technologies, and outreach - each region can accelerate its shift toward a resilient circular nutrient system. The achievements of NOVAFERT so far, and the solid groundwork it has laid, offer a promising blueprint for the future. They suggest that Europe's vision of sustainable fertiliser use is steadily becoming a reality, one region at a time, with lessons learned in one place inspiring progress in another.

To track the technological side, NOVAFERT's living dashboard rates five flagship recovery routes- ammonia stripping-scrubbing, membrane concentration, thermal conversion, mechanical separation, and desalination/dewatering/granulation-across four dimensions of readiness (technical, market, agronomic, sustainability). The latest snapshot shows several standout performers: stripping-scrubbing has reached full pilot deployment with nutrient-recovery rates around 75 % and proven crop benefits, thermal conversion is already commercial-scale with 100 % nutrient retention, and mechanical separation is operating on large farms while cutting emissions versus mineral fertilisers. Even the newer membrane and granulation lines are posting high sustainability scores, though their costs still need to fall before mass adoption. By updating these indicators as projects scale and rules evolve, the dashboard gives policymakers, investors, and farmers a clear, real-time view of which technologies are ready to drive Europe's circular-fertiliser future.

1. Introduction

The NOVAFERT project has emerged as a result of growing concerns about resource depletion, environmental impact, and long-term sustainability in the agricultural sector. In many regions across Europe, dependence on synthetic fertilisers has contributed to nutrient imbalances in the soil, a decline in soil fertility, and increased greenhouse gas emissions. At the same time, geopolitical uncertainties and market fluctuations have highlighted the vulnerability of European agriculture to disruptions in fertiliser supply chains. Recognising these challenges, NOVAFERT aims to accelerate the adoption of alternative fertilisers and nutrient-recovery technologies that can contribute to a more circular economy, reducing dependence on conventional fertilisers.

The overarching goal of NOVAFERT is to create region-specific strategies referred to as Regional Specific Action Plans (RSAPs) that address local barriers, leverage unique opportunities, and align with the ecological, social, and economic conditions of each participating region. These action plans collectively reinforce the project's broader objectives, which include:

- Promoting sustainable agricultural practices by reducing reliance on conventional, resource-intensive fertilisers
- Facilitating nutrient recovery from organic waste, manure, digestate, or sludge, thereby transforming waste streams into valuable fertiliser products
- Supporting policy alignment and harmonisation at local, national, and EU levels
- Enhancing stakeholder engagement, from farmers and policymakers to researchers and private-sector entities, ensuring that solutions reflect real-world conditions and needs

To achieve these objectives, NOVAFERT integrates a structured, participatory approach that draws on input from Regional Working Groups (RWGs), policymakers, industry partners, and academic experts. Regular workshops, surveys, and consultations ensure that the RSAPs capture both quantitative metrics such as funding allocations and nitrogen or phosphorus recycling rates and qualitative insights, including stakeholder perceptions and sociopolitical willingness to adopt new fertiliser technologies. This combination of numerical data and lived experiences allows the RSAPs to serve as *tailored, actionable roadmaps* for each region.

Table 1. summarizes the eight priority areas and their corresponding focus within the NOVAFERT framework, providing a clear overview of the project's scope

Priority Area	Focus
Legal Framework	Aligning local legislation with EU directives, ensuring that alternative fertiliser products meet health, safety, and environmental standards
Political Willingness	Engaging policymakers to support alternative fertilisers through public funding, regulatory reforms, or awareness campaigns

Research & Development	Strengthening collaborations between universities, research institutes, and industry partners to foster innovation in fertiliser formulations, environmental monitoring, and scaling methodologies
New Business Models	Encouraging private-sector involvement, market-based incentives, and entrepreneurial initiatives that can bring alternative fertilizing products to market more effectively
Financial Incentives	Developing subsidies, tax benefits, grants, or other support mechanisms to reduce the economic risk for farmers transitioning away from mineral fertilisers
Self-Sufficiency	Enhancing local nutrient cycles, allowing regions to rely more on internal resources like manure or organic residues rather than imported fertilisers
Public Acceptance	Building awareness and trust among farmers, consumers, and local communities so that alternative fertilisers are accepted as safe, effective, and environmentally beneficial
Environmental Protection	Ensuring that alternative fertilisers contribute to soil health, biodiversity, and reduced nutrient losses, key elements in preventing eutrophication, groundwater pollution, and other environmental impacts

Underpinning these eight areas of focus is a monitoring framework that tracks actions and measures progress on a six-point scale, from not initiated (1) to fully completed (6). This monitoring process enables each region to evaluate its performance, identify bottlenecks, and fine-tune strategies in real time providing an iterative cycle of improvement. By sharing these results across the consortium, NOVAFERT encourages knowledge exchange and fosters a common pool of best practices that can be adapted in varied contexts across Europe.

Furthermore, as part of the project's forward-looking vision, NOVAFERT has established a dashboard to communicate the readiness and performance of five priority nutrient-recovery technologies, including stripping and scrubbing, thermal/hydrothermal conversion, membrane-based approaches, mechanical separation, and desalination/dewatering/granulation. The dashboard, which integrates key indicators such as Technology Readiness Level (TRL), Market and Investment Readiness Level (MRL), Agronomic Performance Readiness Level (APRL), and Sustainability Readiness Level (SRL), will serve as an evolving resource. It can be updated throughout and beyond the project as new data, pilot studies, and regulatory changes come to light.

By combining targeted regional strategies with robust technology assessments, NOVAFERT supports a multidimensional transformation of Europe's fertiliser landscape.

2. Methodology

2.1 Monitoring Regional Action Plan

The NOVAFERT project has adopted a comprehensive scoring mechanism to monitor the progress of actions outlined in the RSAPs. This report delves into the scoring the progress, identifying regional performance across eight priority (as reported in D3.3) areas and highlighting the most progressing action in each region. Scores are based on a range from 1 (not started) to 6 (fully implemented)

The methodology for monitoring the progress of the NOVAFERT RSAPs integrates a structured, multi-dimensional approach aimed at capturing the nuances of regional implementation. A standardized scoring framework was employed to evaluate the progress of each action item under the RSAPs. Using a scale of 1 to 6, the framework captures stages from initial planning to full implementation. The evaluation encompassed eight priority areas, including Legal Framework, Political Willingness, Research and Technical Development, and Environmental Protection. Each region's unique challenges and opportunities were factored into the scoring.

The scoring system for the NOVAFERT project utilizes a six-point scale to evaluate the progress of action plans, providing a comprehensive framework for tracking implementation status. A score of **1 (Not Initiated)** indicates that no steps have been taken to begin the action, with resources, stakeholders, and plans yet to be developed. A score of **2 (Initial Planning Stage)** signifies that preparatory activities have commenced, including stakeholder identification and resource allocation, though tangible progress is not yet evident. Progress accelerates at **3 (In Progress - Early Phase)**, where implementation begins, minor milestones are achieved, and initial outputs such as workshops or stakeholder engagement are visible. At **4 (Substantial Progress)**, the majority of planned actions are underway, with significant advancements and key deliverables produced, supported by active stakeholder engagement. A score of **5 (Near Completion)** reflects that most objectives have been achieved, with only final adjustments or evaluations pending. Finally, a score of **6 (Fully Completed)** denotes that the action plan is entirely implemented, all objectives and deliverables have been met, and results have been documented and confirmed through evaluations. This structured scoring system ensures clarity and consistency in assessing progress across different regions and priority areas.

Data collection was a foundation of the approach, involving regional stakeholders such as policymakers, researchers, and farmers. Information was gathered through participatory workshops, surveys, and consultations, ensuring a diverse set of insights. Progress reports and feedback from previous deliverables were integrated to provide a continuous and comprehensive assessment. Both quantitative metrics, such as nutrient recycling volumes and funding allocations, and qualitative insights, like stakeholder perceptions, were considered in the evaluation process.

The monitoring timeline facilitated periodic evaluation, enabling comparative analysis of progress across regions. Scores were analysed to identify trends, barriers, and high-performing actions, and insights were used to develop targeted recommendations for addressing barriers.

This structured and inclusive methodology ensures effective monitoring and supports the scaling of successful practices across regions.

Table 2. Shows the strategic scoring system

Score	Description	Criteria	Indicators
1	Not Initiated	No steps have been taken to begin the action. The necessary resources, stakeholders, and plans have not been initiated.	
2	Initial Planning Stage	Early planning and preparatory activities have begun, but no concrete progress on implementation. Resources and stakeholders have been identified.	Meetings held, stakeholders identified, resources allocated, but no tangible outcomes yet.
3	In Progress (Early Phase)	Action plan implementation has started, but progress is still limited. Minor milestones may have been reached, and early outputs are visible.	Preliminary activities underway (e.g., workshops, stakeholder engagement), initial results starting to emerge.
4	Substantial Progress	Significant progress toward key milestones. The majority of planned actions are underway, and there is tangible evidence of advancement.	Majority of activities in progress, several deliverables/outputs produced, key stakeholders actively engaged.
5	Near Completion	The action is almost completed with most objectives achieved, though final steps and some minor tasks remain.	Major milestones completed, most deliverables/outputs finalized, final evaluations or adjustments in process.
6	Fully Completed	The action plan is fully implemented, with all objectives, deliverables, and expected outcomes achieved.	All tasks and actions are completed, results documented, and evaluations confirming success.

2.2 Dashboard Indicator

Further, as part of the NovaFert project’s objective to promote and implement novel nutrient-recovery solutions, five priority technologies have been selected across several participating regions. These technologies, along with associated products and processes, must be communicated effectively to a diverse set of stakeholders, including agricultural producers, policymakers, investors, and researchers.

To facilitate stakeholder engagement and illustrate the current performance and maturity of these technologies, a dashboard with carefully chosen indicators has been developed. This dashboard not only displays technology-specific data in a user-friendly format but also serves as a living document-the indicator values can be updated throughout and beyond the project’s

lifespan. In this way, the dashboard remains a relevant and evolving resource that can inform subsequent initiatives.

The five key nutrient-recovery and resource-utilization technologies featured in NovaFert are:

1. Stripping and Scrubbing (Belgium)
2. Thermal / Hydrothermal Conversion (Poland)
3. Membrane-Based Technology (Catalonia)
4. Mechanical separation (Finland)
5. Desalination, dewatering, granulation (Ireland)

Each of these technologies addresses specific challenges related to nutrient recovery and waste management while offering distinct pathways for producing innovative fertiliser products.

To provide a robust yet concise snapshot of each technology's performance and suitability for agricultural application, eight indicators have been selected. These indicators encapsulate the essential aspects of efficiency, compliance, and impact:

1. Readiness Level: Reflects the multi-dimensional maturity of the technology
2. Nutrient Recovery Rate (NRR): Quantifies the proportion of total nutrients (e.g., nitrogen, phosphorus) effectively recovered.
3. Emission Reduction Compared to Synthetic Fertiliser: Shows the relative decrease in emissions when using the recovered fertiliser product compared to conventional synthetic fertilisers.
4. Nutrient Use Efficiency (NUE): Assesses how effectively the recovered product's nutrients are utilized by crops, influencing yield and environmental footprint.
5. FPR Compliance: Fertilising Products Regulation demonstrates whether the product meets EU Fertilising Products Regulation requirements for safety, quality, and labelling.
6. PFC Label: Product Function Category designates the specific functional category under which the recovered fertiliser is classified under the EU regulatory framework.
7. Compositional Parameters: Includes critical chemical properties (e.g., N, P, K) that define suitability for agricultural application.

By consolidating these indicators, stakeholders gain a well-rounded understanding of the technology's status, environmental benefits, agronomic performance, and compliance with relevant regulations.

A key innovation in the NovaFert dashboard is the **multi-dimensional readiness level** framework. While Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is a widely used measure of maturity, NovaFert expands this concept to include additional dimensions that are crucial for successful market uptake and sustainable implementation:

- 1) Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

- Definition: Evaluates the technical maturity of a technology, ranging from initial proof-of-concept (TRL 1-3) to pilot/validation (TRL 4-6) and finally to system-level demonstration and commercialization (TRL 7-9).
 - Rationale: Offers insight into how close the technology is to full-scale deployment.
- 2) Market and Investment Readiness Level (MRL)
- Definition: Assesses the technology's commercial viability, including market demand, investment attractiveness, and business model maturity.
 - Rationale: Addresses the economic and financial aspects, indicating whether the technology can be profitably scaled and adopted by industry stakeholders.
- 3) Agronomic Performance Readiness Level (APL)
- Definition: Examines how effectively the recovered product performs in real-world agricultural settings, considering crop yield response, nutrient availability, and user acceptance by farmers.
 - Rationale: Ensures that the technology or product delivers tangible agronomic benefits and is practical for end-users.
- 4) Sustainable Readiness Level (SRL)
- Definition: Evaluates the environmental and societal sustainability of the technology, including greenhouse gas emission reductions, resource circularity, and potential impact on soil health and biodiversity.
 - Rationale: Reflects the broader ecological and social implications, highlighting the long-term viability and alignment with sustainability goals.

To make the readiness level concept both intuitive and actionable, a scoring system is employed for each dimension. Annex 2 defines the criteria for assigning scores (e.g., on a 1-9) within each readiness dimension. Below is a general outline:

- Score 1-3:
 - TRL: Early-stage lab research or small-scale experiments
 - MRL: No business model, limited market analysis
 - APL: Limited field testing, insufficient agronomic data
 - SRL: Uncertain sustainability impacts, no formal assessment
- Score 4-6:
 - TRL: Working prototypes or pilot-scale validation
 - MRL: Developing business strategy, initial investor interest
 - APL: Some field trials, moderate agronomic performance data

- SRL: Preliminary life-cycle assessment or environmental impact studies
- Score 7-9:
 - TRL: Demonstration in relevant environments or full commercial deployment
 - MRL: Established market presence, sustained investment flow, clear revenue model
 - APL: Comprehensive agronomic performance data, strong farmer adoption
 - SRL: Documented positive environmental outcomes, alignment with EU directives

3. Results

3.1 Monitoring Regional Action Plan

3.1.1 Flanders (Belgium)

The NOVAFERT project's action plans for Flanders are showing encouraging momentum overall, with the majority of initiatives either well-established or making steady progress. For instance, the multi-stakeholder engagement efforts (B3 and B11) have been particularly successful, leading to frequent steering group meetings, thematic workshops, and a flow of new ideas. Similarly, public dissemination of BBF-related information (B2 and B7) is robust, largely due to consistent communication via the Nutricycle Vlaanderen platform, newsletters, and social media. Research activities (B4 and B14) are also advancing, aided by ongoing conferences, updated inventories of scientific findings, and field validations via scientific partnerships.

Within these priority areas, several actions are moving quickly. Under Legal Framework (Actions B1, B2), the dissemination of policy developments and best practices is well underway; a steady stream of newsletters, social media updates, and event participation ensures consistent stakeholder awareness. Efforts to solidify Political Willingness (B3) have likewise progressed well, as the Multi-Stakeholder Task Force meets regularly to coordinate goals and strategies. Efforts to foster public-private partnerships (B6) are progressing well in the context of multiple EU projects, bringing together fertiliser companies, agritech startups, and research institutions. In New Business Models (B7), the first-line advice "counter function" is effectively serving as a contact point for questions on nutrient recovery. Moreover, Self-Sufficiency (B10) benefits from ongoing pilot projects and demonstrations in on-farm manure management and composting, helping build local expertise. Meanwhile, Environmental Protection (B13, B14) has seen ongoing research on precision fertilisation and bio-based fertilisers, supported by technology developments to monitor nitrogen losses and soil conditions. Additionally, the systemic scenario analyses for more sustainable N, P, and protein flows (B5) have made headway with new modeling tools and dashboards under development. These advancements help clarify where the biggest nutrient inefficiencies lie and where circular solutions can be most impactful.

A few areas, however, are progressing more slowly. Under New Business Models, the plan to draft a Green Deal (B8) remains in a conceptual phase, with no concrete framework yet in place despite stakeholder enthusiasm. Similarly, Financial Incentives (B9) is lagging behind, as it involves complex legislative and budgetary considerations to create workable tax incentives, preferential financing, or subsidies. While initial discussions have identified possible avenues for support, further policy alignment and stakeholder agreement are needed to move these incentives into a more implementable form.

One notable bottleneck across these slower-moving actions is the need for broader policy alignment and formal approvals, which can be time consuming given multiple layers of governance and regulatory constraints. Designing incentives or deals that fit both EU and Flemish requirements demands careful coordination among policymakers, research

institutions, and industry partners. Nevertheless, interest remains high, and ongoing forums- such as stakeholder task forces and working groups- provide a strong platform to bridge gaps, share expertise, and advance legislation and economic instruments.

Table 3. Overview of Progress Across Eight Priority Areas in Flanders

Priority Area	Action	Progress Score	Comments
Legal Framework	B1. Incentive policy ((Interdisciplinary collaboration, removing legal barriers, leading by example, researching legislation))	5	Work in progress, part of a long-term vision (by 2050).Next steps: Continue current activities.
Legal Framework	B2. Communication & Dissemination (Nutricycle Vlaanderen platform, social media, newsletters, brochures, policy briefs)	5	Main dissemination activities through website/social media and partner events. Next steps: Set up a newsletter.
Political Willingness	B3. Establish a Multi-Stakeholder Task Force (Identify key stakeholders, schedule meetings, assign advocacy roles)	6	Steering group meets three times per year. Next steps: Continue the steering group.
Research & Tech Dev.	B4. Flanders as a European knowledge region (Updated research inventory, conferences, inter-university cooperation, translation of international research)	6	Nutricycle Vlaanderen website is kept up to date. Next steps: Ongoing events (ManuREsource, ESNI) and scientific collaborations.
Research & Tech Dev.	B5. Systemic scenario analysis (Inventory of N & P flows, modeling shifts in nutrient/protein flows, recording indicators)	5	Ongoing (2023–2026). Next steps: Creation of a protein dashboard.
Research & Tech Dev.	B6. Foster Public–Private Partnerships (Identify private sector partners, facilitate collaboration, promote joint ventures/funding for BBF)	5	Conducted within multiple EU projects. Next steps: Continue building partnerships with fertiliser companies and agritech startups.
New Business Models	B7. "Counter function" for first-line advice (A digital/contact point for nutrient recovery info)	6	A general email address is established; several inquiries have been answered or referred. Next steps: Keep following up on incoming questions.

New Business Models	B8. Drawing up a Green Deal (Catalysis and monitoring by Nutricycle Flanders)	2	Proposed during a meeting, but no concrete action yet. Next steps: Launch a new proposal to draft a Green Deal.
Financial Incentives	B9. Provision of economic incentives (Awareness campaigns, tax exemptions, preferential financing for alt fertiliser infrastructure)	4	Part of Werkagenda bioeconomie Vlaanderen Circulair. Next steps: Continue discussions in the steering group.
Self Sufficiency	B10. Optimised manure management (Monitoring nutrient management, pocket digesters, composting, support local partnerships)	5	Various projects supported (Boost, ChicoryREpowered). Next steps: Ongoing efforts to improve on-farm nutrient cycles.
Public Acceptance	B11. Stakeholder interaction (Working groups, workshops, thematic sessions, etc.)	6	Working groups established; Next steps: Continue organizing workshops and demonstration events
Public Acceptance	B12. Info to farmers on RENURE & new organo-mineral fertilisers (Targeted docs, workshops/webinars, demos)	6	Already implemented via Nutricycle; recurring topic in workshops/events. Next steps: Project ReMestV (VCM & Inagro).
Environmental Protection	B13. Precision agriculture (Set up a precision fertilisation centre, develop variable fertilisation tech, soil management)	5	Ongoing efforts. Next steps: Continue refining and promoting precision fertilisation technologies.
Environmental Protection	B14. Research on agronomic & environmental performance (Monitor N losses, quality of bio-based mineral N, practical field validation)	5	Some analyses done; ongoing under various programs. Next steps: Continue real-world trials and data collection.

Figure 1. Radar Chart Illustrating Progress Across Priority Areas in Flanders

3.1.2 Croatia

Many actions show clear momentum, especially in Public Acceptance (C11) and Environmental Protection (C12). Field days, workshops, and social media campaigns (C11) are rolling out on schedule, drawing attention to alternative fertilisers and engaging both farmers and the general public. In parallel, educational content and success stories are being shared (C12), sparking constructive dialogue about environmental sustainability. Meanwhile, under Political Willingness (C3, C4), efforts to foster partnerships between government bodies, NGOs, and the private sector are well underway; cross-sector working groups and knowledge-exchange tours have been proposed to broaden support for alternative fertiliser adoption.

Actions related to the Legal Framework (C1, C2) and Research & Development (C5, C6) have also gained traction. Collaboration with local agricultural associations (C1) is helping identify regulatory hurdles that slow adoption of alternative fertilisers, while knowledge transfer from other EU countries (C2) ensures Croatia can learn from proven frameworks. On the research front, awareness campaigns (C5) and comparative studies (C6) are raising interest in the benefits of alternative products, highlighting differences in environmental impact, cost-effectiveness, and performance compared to traditional fertilisers.

While these efforts are promising, some initiatives require further momentum. Under New Business Models (C7, C8), the planned market research and awareness campaigns are in progress but need additional resources and stakeholder participation, particularly in designing and distributing surveys to gather firsthand data from farmers and agricultural suppliers. Similarly, Financial Incentives (C9) depends on securing grants from EU agricultural funds or other sources; establishing contacts, attending workshops, and navigating application processes have proven time intensive. Lastly, while progress in Self-Sufficiency (C10) is ongoing, more robust demonstration projects and farmer feedback channels could enhance adoption rates.

Overall, Croatia’s action plan is on a positive track, with public-facing activities showing particularly good uptake. However, accelerating market research, solidifying financial supports, and continuing to align with EU best practices will be crucial to ensure long-term impact. In the next six months, teams should prioritize finalizing surveys (C7), expanding collaborative partnerships (C3), and tapping into targeted funding opportunities (C9). Sustained coordination across government, industry, and research institutions remains essential for turning these plans into durable, scalable solutions for alternative fertiliser use.

Table 4. Overview of Progress Across Eight Priority Areas in Croatia

Priority Area	Action	Progress Score	Comments
Legal Framework	C1. Advocate for regulatory adjustments (Establish collaborative partnerships, conduct research, launch awareness campaigns)	5	Attend workshops to address regulatory issues; share information on the e-OPG platform to facilitate knowledge exchange.
Legal Framework	C2. Transfer knowledge about successful EU regulatory frameworks (Identify best practices, attend exchange programs, maintain an information-sharing platform)	5	Same as C1-attend workshops on regulatory issues; share info on e-OPG for ongoing best-practice exchange.
Political Willingness	C3. Foster partnerships (government, private sector, NGOs)(Engage stakeholders, form cross-sector working groups, conduct public awareness campaigns)	5	Organize RWG meetings to promote alternative fertilisers; write an article on their benefits.
Political Willingness	C4. Knowledge exchange campaign (Partner with successful countries, arrange study tours/workshops, evaluate and disseminate findings)	4	Attend international workshops to learn alternative fertiliser methods; share knowledge with local farmers.
Research & Tech Dev.	C5. Raise awareness via R&D findings (Create brochures, simplify technical info, highlight successful case studies)	3	Create an easy-to-understand brochure about alternative fertiliser benefits; share it on e-OPG and other platforms (Facebook, LinkedIn).
Research & Tech Dev.	C6. Compile studies comparing traditional vs. alternative fertilisers (Summarise key findings, engage experts, produce an overview)	3	Organize/attend workshops or webinars to gather expert insights; synthesize data on performance, environmental impact, and cost-effectiveness.

New Business Models	C7. Conduct market research on fertiliser landscape in Croatia (Access data, distribute surveys, list major suppliers)	4	Collect and analyze survey data on stakeholder needs (“What do stakeholders seek in novel fertilisers?”); disseminate consumer surveys, engage participants.
New Business Models	C8. Implement awareness campaigns on alternative fertilisers (Develop educational materials, showcase case studies/testimonials, leverage social media)	5	Write an article on benefits; organize a participatory workshop; share videos at local ag events; post success stories on the e-OPG platform.
Financial Incentives	C9. Explore funding opportunities (EU, international bodies) for sustainable agriculture (Attend info sessions, maintain relationships, publicise funding successes)	4	Share information on relevant “green” tenders and calls; organize webinars to disseminate knowledge and encourage best environmental practices.
Self-Sufficiency	C10. Promote alternative fertilisers for self-sufficiency (Develop educational materials on cost savings, soil health, local language resources)	4	Host local events and demos showcasing benefits; collect feedback via surveys/focus groups to refine outreach strategies.
Public Acceptance	C11. Public awareness campaigns (Organize field days at demo sites, workshops for farmers, targeted social media campaigns)	4	Organize two lighthouse (LH) demo visits; share key outcomes from the NOVAFERT project with the public and stakeholders.
Environmental Protection	C12. Raise public awareness on environmental benefits (Use social media for local challenges, share success stories/impact reports)	5	Continue sharing success stories, brochures, videos; invite stakeholders to participate in surveys for further research.

Figure 2. Radar Chart Illustrating Progress Across Priority Areas in Croatia

3.1.3 Finland

Most of Finland’s actions are set to begin or scale up from 2025 onward, reflecting a forward-looking strategy to introduce and expand alternative fertiliser usage. Certain initiatives are already advancing well at the planning and partnership stage, namely under Legal Framework (F1) and Political Willingness (F2). Collaboration with a company producing alternative fertilisers is scheduled to start in 2025, and environmental demonstration activities are likewise gearing up to showcase the agronomic efficiency of these new products. Efforts in Public Acceptance (F7) have also gained momentum, with ongoing awareness campaigns highlighting food safety considerations that resonate with consumers and stakeholders alike.

One critical area, Legal Framework (F1), focuses on enhancing nutrient recycling subsidies by mapping regional nutrient sources and identifying gaps in the supply chain. This action is still in the early stages, with collaboration planned between producers of alternative fertilisers to address logistical and supply chain challenges. Demonstration activities (F2) to prove environmental benefits are on track for 2025, paving the way for more substantial buy-in from policymakers and farmers. Similarly, awareness-raising on food safety (F7) under Public Acceptance is proceeding, ensuring the public remains informed about both the benefits and any potential risks of alternative fertilisers. In terms of Political Willingness (F2), Finland is making strides to demonstrate the environmental benefits of substituting mineral fertilisers with alternatives. Collaboration with policymakers and evidence-based studies on agronomic efficiency are key components of this action. With progress scored at 4, Finland has laid the groundwork for effective collaboration and advocacy, with detailed implementation set to take place during 2025.

A number of actions lie in a more moderate stage of progress, particularly those under Research & Development (F3), New Business Models (F4), Financial Incentives (F5), and Environmental Protection (F8). For instance, refining nutrient ratios (F3) requires coordinated

R&D with fertiliser companies to ensure alternative formulas align with diverse crop requirements. Meanwhile, transforming side-streams into valuable fertilisers (F4) calls for increased production capacity, an effort that can be slowed by technical and logistical considerations. To develop cost-effective logistics (F5), stakeholder workshops will help identify bottlenecks and create incentives. Lastly, fully demonstrating the potential reduction in N and P losses using alternative fertilisers (F8) require field trials and robust data collection, which will take time to set up.

In the next six months, the focus should be on solidifying collaborations with fertiliser producers (F1, F3), scheduling demonstration trials (F2, F8), and convening workshops or discussion forums to address logistics and cost hurdles (F5). Gathering and disseminating farmer opinions (F6) will also be crucial to refining strategies for replacing mineral fertilisers. By strengthening these aspects now, Finland’s plan will be better positioned for significant, long-term gains when the major activities ramp up in 2025 and beyond.

Table 5. Overview of Progress Across Eight Priority Areas in Finland

Priority Area	Action	Progress Score	Comments
Legal Framework	F1. Uptake of nutrient recycling subsidy for manure-based nutrients	4	Collaboration with a company producing alternative fertilisers starts in 2025.
Political Willingness	F2. Demonstrate environmental benefits of substituting mineral fertilisers	5	Agronomic efficiency trials continue in 2025; results to be shared with stakeholders.
Research & Technical Dev.	F3. Supplement alternative fertilisers with additional nutrients	2	Evaluating the correct NP ratio begins in 2025, in collaboration with fertiliser companies.
New Business Models	F4. Turn nutrient-rich side-streams into valuable fertilisers	2	Awareness-raising ongoing; a framework for supporting production is still in early development.
Financial Incentives	F5. Develop economic incentives to reduce logistics costs	3	Logistics barriers under review; workshops planned with farmers, producers, and policymakers.
Self-Sufficiency	F6. Enhanced replacement of mineral fertilisers with alternative ones	4	Gathering farmer opinions; reducing restrictions on manure-based alternatives is in progress.
Public Acceptance	F7. Increase awareness about food safety when using alternative fertilisers	5	Assessing risks and disseminating safety information; public outreach continues in 2025.
Environmental Protection	F8. Reduce use of mineral fertilisers by	2	Determining acceptable N/P loss limits; comparative trials with

	switching to alternative fertilisers		mineral vs. alternative fertilisers to start.
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Figure 3. Radar Chart Illustrating Progress Across Priority Areas in Finland

3.1.4 Ireland

Ireland’s plan is advancing well on multiple fronts, with many actions scheduled for or already underway in 2024. Under the Legal Framework (I1-I3), there is ongoing work to harmonize national and European legislation, explore carbon credit incentives, and encourage efficient nutrient exchange between livestock and tillage farms. While progress in these areas is still in early stages (scored 2-3), ongoing collaboration with stakeholders is ensuring steady advancement-demonstration farms and media outreach have succeeded in informing both farmers and the broader public about the benefits of alternative fertilisers.

Key steps are being made in Research & Development (I5-I7). Scientific field experiments testing different types of alternative fertilisers are ongoing (led by TEAGASC), and training days for advisors and teachers are helping integrate new findings into formal education programs. Meanwhile, New Business Models (I8) focus on building industry-research relationships, with several collaborative agreements in progress. Early efforts on Financial Incentives (I9) show promise, as Teagasc is actively looking to encourage policy measures and tax benefits that could accelerate farmer adoption. Similarly, improving nutrient use efficiency (I10) under Self-Sufficiency emphasizes leveraging farm-available resources and manure management, which ties into the country’s broader sustainability goals.

Strong stakeholder engagement efforts are underway, particularly under Public Acceptance (I11-I13). Lighthouse demonstration farms and success stories circulated via social media have been well-received, boosting visibility for alternatives to chemical fertilisers. On the Environmental Protection side (I14-I15), field trials continue to measure and demonstrate how alternative fertilisers affect soil health and nutrient losses, with plans to keep sharing research

outcomes through advisory services and demonstration visits. By solidifying these communication channels, Ireland’s plan is well positioned to maintain momentum in the year ahead.

While these efforts are promising, some initiatives require further momentum. While there is clear awareness of the benefits of alternative fertilisers, especially the role of adding soil carbon, Actions I2 (introducing carbon credit incentives) and I9 (expanding government incentives) remain relatively preliminary. The primary challenge is establishing concrete legislation or clear financial mechanisms that reward farmers for adopting alternatives. The plan notes that the link to policy is not yet strong, indicating a gap between scientific evidence (e.g., on carbon sequestration) and formal policy instruments such as tax credits, carbon markets, or targeted subsidies. Although there is mention of encouraging livestock-tillage partnerships for exchanging nutrients (I3), the plan highlights ongoing efforts rather than fully operational systems. This coordination requires advisory services, advanced planning, and strict nutrient management guidelines so that organic manures can be used without breaching nitrogen-limit rules. Without robust logistical frameworks or incentives, smaller-scale or stockless farms can find it difficult to collaborate with livestock farms, meaning valuable nutrient sources might remain underutilized.

Looking forward, the next six months will focus on fine-tuning economic incentives (I9), expanding demonstration activities (I4, I11), and advancing collaborative R&D with industry (I6, I8). Additionally, deeper exploration of carbon credits (I2) and best-practice application guidelines (I15) can help steer policy discussions, ensuring that alternative fertilisers align with both environmental goals and farmer needs. As these measures strengthen, Ireland’s action plan stands to produce tangible, long-term benefits in nutrient management and rural sustainability.

Table 6. Overview of Progress Across Eight Priority Areas in Ireland

Priority Area	Action	Progress Score	Comments
Legal Framework	I1. National legislation complies with European legislation on the use of alternative fertilisers	2	Continue collaborating with stakeholders and projects working on legal harmonisation.
Legal Framework	I2. Introduce carbon credit incentives for farmers	2	Benefits of adding soil carbon via bio-based fertilisers demonstrated, but weak policy link; further stakeholder collaboration needed.
Legal Framework	I3. Encourage livestock/tillage partnerships for nutrient exchange	4	Ongoing dissemination to advisors; aiming to improve nutrient management planning between livestock and stockless farms.
Political Willingness	I4. Public awareness and education campaigns	6	Extensive information delivered via demonstration farms, workshops, and seminars; strong stakeholder engagement.

Research & Technical Development	15. Provide scientific research for displacing chemical fertilisers with alternatives	6	Field experiments by Teagasc demonstrate various alternative fertilisers; research findings shared with advisors and agricultural colleges.
Research & Technical Development	16. Support mechanisms for local production of alternative fertilisers	4	Collaboration with stakeholders and other projects continues; focusing on grant aid alignment for nutrient refining technologies.
Research & Technical Development	17. Provide more information to advisory services about the bioeconomy	6	In-service training days for teachers/advisors have taken place; ongoing updates on research findings.
New Business Models	18. Collaboration between research and companies	4	Building relationships and seeking funding for joint projects; continuing to collaborate with stakeholders.
Financial Incentives	19. Government provides economic incentives to farmers using alternative fertilisers	1	Teagasc is starting to explore and encourage financial incentives; policy framework is in very early stages.
Self Sufficiency	110. Provide tools for farmers to optimize on-farm nutrients	6	Information disseminated on crop rotation, manure management, and bio-based fertiliser benefits; ongoing advisory support.
Public Acceptance	111. Raise awareness via demonstration farms, videos, success stories	6	NOVAFERT lighthouse demonstrations shared with farmers and the public; continued outreach planned.
Public Acceptance	112. Public awareness campaign	4	Outputs from the forthcoming MOOC will be used in educational settings; continued focus on community events and social media.
Public Acceptance	113. Case studies/success stories	6	Sharing farmer success stories on social media channels; strong engagement among peer farmers and consumers.
Environmental Protection	114. Promote the benefits of alternative fertilisers on soil health	6	Field measurements continue at the Irish lighthouse demo; positive results on soil health being communicated to stakeholders.
Environmental Protection	115. Use fertiliser at the right time, rate, and place	6	Ongoing dissemination of best practices to minimise nutrient losses; research findings shared through advisory services.

Figure 4. Radar Chart Illustrating Progress Across Priority Areas in Ireland

3.1.5 Catalonia

Catalonia has launched a broad set of measures to boost the valorisation of organic by-products into alternative fertilisers. Under the Legal Framework (Ca1-Ca6), authorities and stakeholders are working on amending national and regional regulations (e.g., Law 7/2022), addressing end-of-waste criteria, and seeking recognition for RENURE products. Several proposals and discussions with the Spanish government and EU bodies are underway, showing strong willingness to align Catalonian practices with broader European directives. Meanwhile, the region is advancing new policy proposals, particularly on reducing logistical barriers and fostering centralised treatment plants for manure and other by-products.

Catalonia's Political Willingness (Ca7-Ca12) is reflected in efforts to catalogue and characterise regional waste streams, build a "Catalonian bioeconomy-hub," and simplify licensing for new valorisation plants. There is also forward motion on establishing a Catalonian Nutrient Platform (Ca11), with stakeholder mapping completed and initial funding secured. In Research & Development (Ca13-Ca16), demonstration projects and operative groups are funded every two years, helping test new technologies for recovering nutrients from digestate and other organic streams. These initiatives have begun to generate data on alternative fertiliser efficacy, lending credibility to broader adoption efforts.

A few actions remain in the early stages or face structural hurdles. For instance, establishing new end-points in animal by-products regulation (Ca6) has not advanced substantially, as regional workshops did not identify it as a top priority for industry stakeholders. Comprehensive catalogues of all waste streams (Ca7-Ca9) and the further development of shared infrastructures (Ca21) are also pending, partly due to the complexity of collecting accurate volume and composition data. Additionally, while there is clear interest in establishing new business models (Ca17-Ca21), the actual deployment of carbon credits, eco-labelling frameworks, and fully shared processing facilities is still in the conceptual or pilot phase.

In Research and Technical Development, significant progress has been made through demonstrative projects and operational research groups, primarily funded by EU CAP. Studies are evaluating the feasibility of alternative fertilisers, the cost-effectiveness of new processing methods, and strategies to improve nutrient recovery. Despite these advances, bottlenecks include high production costs and technical uncertainties, which hinder the market readiness of alternative fertilisers. To address this, upcoming research efforts will focus on practical applications and cost reductions to enhance adoption by farmers and agricultural industries. Similarly, financial incentives are being developed to construct new bio-waste treatment plants, with funding allocated for 12 new facilities annually.

Over the next six months, the focus should be on formalising the legal status of alternative fertilisers and addressing end-of-waste challenges (Ca3, Ca4), continuing to streamline licensing procedures (Ca9), and finalising targets for manure-treatment infrastructure (Ca10). Completing a robust waste catalogue (Ca7-Ca8) will facilitate more accurate planning and support business networking (Ca19). Further demonstration trials (Ca13-Ca16) will also be essential to validate technology performance and build public confidence (Ca27-Ca28). By coordinating across government agencies, industry, and research institutions, Catalonia can turn these initiatives into a resilient circular-nutrient system that benefits both agriculture and the environment.

Table 7. Overview of Progress Across Eight Priority Areas in Catalonia

Priority Area	Action (What will we do?)	Progress Score	Comments / Plans
Legal Framework	Ca1. Revision of normative limitations (collective by-product valorisation plants)	1	After regional workshops, a safer solution is to replace outdated farms with manure treatment plants (rather than reducing biosecurity distance).
Legal Framework	Ca2. Proposal to amend National waste regulation (Law 7/2022) for fertilisers not in EU 2019/1009	1	Discussed in international platforms to harmonise transformation processes and define end-of-waste status.
Legal Framework	Ca3. Proposal to amend National waste regulation to allow certain organic by-products for alternative fertilisers	3	End-of-waste for sludge is complicated by references to FPR; Catalan Gov. is in conversation with Spanish Ministries. Commission feedback allows setting national end-points.
Legal Framework	Ca4. Recognition of RENURE products	4	RENURE likely included in the Nitrate Directive Amendment after public consultation (Mar-Apr 2024); Catalan Government gave input with BETA's help.
Legal Framework	Ca5. Promote alternative fertilisers in organic farming	5	Criteria nearly established by Expert Group to accept manure-derived

			products from conventional farms if certain treatments are done.
Legal Framework	Ca6. Promotion of new end-points in manufacturing chain (Reg 1009/2009, 142/2011)	1	No progress; not a critical need per regional workshop. Priority may be revised.
Political Willingness	Ca7. Improve characterisation & distribution of organic by-products	3	A catalogue of technologies/services exists on BioHubCat; waste catalogue with volumes/characteristics still pending.
Political Willingness	Ca8. Develop business network for circular bioeconomy	3	Catalonian Bioeconomy Hub promoted; next steps include completing the waste catalogue.
Political Willingness	Ca9. Shorten & simplify licensing procedures for valorisation plants	3	Coordination among different agencies needed. Low-quality industrial project proposals hamper approval.
Political Willingness	Ca10. Determine targets & implementation model for recovered fertilisers	2	No specific targets yet; identified as a critical need in regional workshops.
Political Willingness	Ca11. Creation of Catalonian Nutrient Platform	3	Funding secured (Demonstrative Activity), stakeholder mapping ongoing.
Political Willingness	Ca12. Promotion of new accredited Notified Bodies (CMCs 3, 5, 12, 13)	1	Currently only one Notified Body in Spain (Seville). Limited interest from producers for EU market.
Research & Tech Dev.	Ca13. Research/demonstration of alternative fertilisers in ag fields	5	Demonstrative & Operative groups in Catalonia address this every two years (EU CAP funds).
Research & Tech Dev.	Ca14. Research on feasibility of alternative processing methods (end-point in manufacturing chain)	5	Covered by Demonstrative & Operative groups in Catalonia (EU CAP funds).
Research & Tech Dev.	Ca15. Studies on techno-economic feasibility of organic by-product treatment	5	Funded every two years via Demonstrative & Operative groups (EU CAP).
Research & Tech Dev.	Ca16. R&I to reduce cost of treatment & valorisation	5	Also addressed by Demonstrative & Operative groups (EU CAP).
New Business Models	Ca17. Creation of rules for a carbon credits market	1	Currently non-existent.

New Business Models	Ca18. Inclusion of sustainable nutrient management in a certification system	1	Also unestablished.
New Business Models	Ca19. Synergies between livestock farmers, waste producers, by-product facilities	4	Conferences (BIT, PRO-FEM, PATT) ongoing; digital platform (BioHubCat) could expand.
New Business Models	Ca20. Promote the market of alternative fertilisers	1	Legal establishment of these fertilisers is the first step; raw manure or synthetic fertiliser currently prioritised.
New Business Models	Ca21. Promotion of intermediate processing units & shared infrastructure	1	Shared infrastructure is limited by legal constraints.
Financial Incentives	Ca22. Public incentives for building by-product treatment plants	5	Catalan Gov. supports constructing ~12 new plants/year. Next step: expand incentives for sanitisation and other treatment units.
Financial Incentives	Ca23. Public subsidies for co-financing by-product treatment plants	5	Same scheme as C22, with new budget lines from 2027-2030.
Self Sufficiency	Ca24. Enhance bio-product production via improved infrastructure	5	Public investment/subsidies for digestate post-processing.
Self Sufficiency	Ca25. Promote self-consumption in industry (anaerobic digestion, biomethane)	2	Focus on energy self-sufficiency (public waste management, wastewater treatment).
Self Sufficiency	Ca26. Incentives for reducing dependence on conflict-zone imports (RENURE, struvite, carbon-rich products)	1	Promotion of self-sufficiency with manure-derived and P-rich products.
Public Acceptance	Ca27. Promote circular bioeconomy model (societal acceptance of by-product transformation)	3	Workshops, seminars to inform public.
Public Acceptance	Ca28. Workshops on alternative fertilisers	6	BIT, PRO-FEM, PATT workshops ongoing; digital platform (BioHubCat) extends reach.

Environmental Protection	Ca29. Develop rules for eco-labelling	1	Eco-labelling framework is in early stages.
Environmental Protection	Ca30. Apply environmental sustainability labels (eco-labels)	1	Guidelines needed for GHG calculation, public certification, and a "Sustainable Agricultural Production" label.
Environmental Protection	Ca31. Promote Best Available Techniques (BAT) to reduce ammonia emissions	2	Catalan-Aragon stakeholders contributing to JRC BREF revisions; funded Operative Groups & Demonstrative Activities.

Figure 5. Radar Chart Illustrating Progress Across Priority Areas in Catalonia

3.1.6 Poland

The results from Poland’s participation in the NOVAFERT project highlight structured efforts across various priority areas. Under the Legal Framework, efforts are focused on reviewing and updating regulations related to alternative fertilisers such as animal manure, digestate, and sewage sludge. Progress is in the early stages, with key national and European regulations being mapped and discussions underway with the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development to implement necessary legal changes. These activities will continue into 2025, with further policy refinements expected.

Efforts to engage local and regional authorities (P2) demonstrate solid political willingness, as multiple RWG meetings have already taken place to highlight environmental benefits and discuss legislative updates at the regional level. Meanwhile, the plan also fosters Research & Development (P3) by mapping out local R&D opportunities and showcasing innovative

technologies through lighthouse visits- all of which have been successfully carried out, providing a strong example of farmer engagement. Research efforts are likewise supported through scientific conferences, most notably, a paper prepared within the NOVAFERT project will be presented at the "12th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management" as well as through funding initiatives and lighthouse visits that highlight innovative soil-improvement technologies using sewage sludge. Notably, four regional workshops have already been successfully organized under the Novafert KPI, where legislative topics were addressed, and broader farmer participation was encouraged.

In terms of New Business Models (P4), initial analyses on transforming waste materials into fertilisers underscore the region's potential for circular economy solutions.

Poland has also made significant progress in Public Acceptance and Financial Incentives (P5) by conducting workshops and stakeholder engagement activities to promote the circular economy in fertiliser production. Efforts are being made to analyze financial support options such as tax relief programs and grants for farmers who adopt alternative fertilisers. Furthermore, a public awareness campaign has been launched, including educational materials and success stories from farmers who have successfully transitioned to using alternative fertilisers. A short educational film is also in development, with its release planned for the first half of 2025 (P7, P8). Likewise, Poland is pursuing Self-Sufficiency (P6) by promoting local raw material use and supporting homegrown fertiliser production.

In terms of Environmental Protection, Poland is collaborating with institutions (P9) such as EurEau and GreenBack to promote sustainable development and mitigate climate change through alternative fertiliser use. Workshops (P10) have been successfully held for farmers, with nearly 80 participants attending, and additional sessions are scheduled for early 2025. Additionally, scientific dissemination (P11) is well underway, with research findings being readied for publication in the first quarter of 2025 (end of April), demonstrating a strong commitment to evidence-based policy and practice.

While most measures are advancing steadily, a few areas need more time or coordination. Finalizing regulatory changes (P1) depends on complex national-level processes, which slows the adoption of updated rules. Similarly, developing robust financial support (P5) and encouraging local raw material usage (P6) require stronger cooperation among farmers, local authorities, and industry. In addition, testing and validating new waste-to-fertiliser technologies (P3) can be time-consuming, since thorough pilot projects and studies are necessary to confirm viability. Overcoming these administrative, technical, and collaborative hurdles will be crucial for meeting long-term goals.

Over the next six months, Poland's action plan will benefit from finalizing regulatory updates (P1), broadening economic support measures (P5), and further developing self-sufficiency strategies (P6). Completing and sharing the educational video (P7) and continuing stakeholder workshops (P8, P10) will be important for maintaining momentum and public trust. At the same time, expanding R&D collaborations (P3) and advancing new circular business models (P4) will support the transition away from mineral fertiliser imports. By synchronizing efforts across all

priority areas, Poland stands to make significant, long-term gains in sustainable nutrient management.

Table 8. Overview of Progress Across Eight Priority Areas in Poland

Priority Area	Action (What will we do?)	Progress Score	Comments / Plans
Legal Framework	P1. Review and update regulations ((animal manure, digestate, sewage sludge))	2	Activities will continue in 2025. Further collaboration with the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development to implement needed legal changes.
Political Willingness	P2. Increase engagement of local/regional authorities ((organize RWG meetings, promote environmental benefits, support legislative initiatives))	4	Two RWG meetings have already taken place, promoting environmental benefits. Two more RWG meetings by April 2024; workshops planned to present regional legislative initiatives to farmers.
Research & Technical Dev.	P3. Support research on new waste-to-fertiliser technologies (identify opportunities, increase R&D funding, organize conferences/workshops)	3	A regional review of research opportunities is done; a lighthouse visit showcased innovative sewage-sludge-to-soil-improver technology. A workshop in early 2025 to address farmer subsidies for alternative fertilisers.
New Business Models	P4. Promote circular economy for converting waste into fertilisers (analyze potential, promote CE frameworks, foster collaborations)	3	Potential for transforming sewage sludge, animal manure, and digestate into marketable fertilisers has been analyzed. Continue activities over the next six months to enhance progress toward circular economy objectives.
Financial Incentives	P5. Implement economic support systems for farmers (analyze funding, develop grants/tax relief, promote available support)	4	Various support options for farmers will be presented at upcoming 2025 workshops. Finalize details of grant/tax relief programs and inform farmers at scheduled events.
Self Sufficiency	P6. Reduce dependence on mineral fertiliser imports (analyze local raw material potential, support local producers, promote self-sufficiency)	4	Actions ongoing; will continue in 2025. Further emphasis on local fertiliser producers and promoting on-farm self-sufficiency.
Public Acceptance	P7. Increase public awareness of alternative fertilisers (educational	4	Materials are being collected for a short educational movie promoting NOVAFERT and secondary-source

	campaigns, collaborate with environmental orgs, share success stories)		fertilisers. Movie production planned for first half of 2025..
Public Acceptance	P8. Inform stakeholders (esp. farmers) about alternative products (workshops, lighthouse visits, show positive impacts, use varied communication channels)	6	Workshops and a lighthouse visit have taken place; farmers gained knowledge about benefits of alternative fertilisers. Communication via social media, email, phone. Continue broad outreach using these channels.
Environmental Protection	P9. Support environmental protection efforts(identify benefits, promote climate-friendly narratives, collaborate with enviro institutions)	6	MEERI collaborates with environmental institutions. RWG includes EurEau and GreenBack to promote sustainable development. Ongoing efforts to highlight the role of alternative fertilisers in environmental protection.
Environmental Protection	P10. Promote best practices for sustainable use	5	Two out of three workshops have been held with ~80 participants; continuous contact with advisors. Next workshop in the first quarter of 2025; continued advisory support for farmers.
Environmental Protection	P11. Publish scientific research on alternative fertilisers (identify key areas, prepare research papers, disseminate findings)	5	An article on the use of alternative fertilisers is in final stages. Publication planned for the first quarter of 2025; results to be shared via conferences, workshops, and other platforms.

Figure 6. Radar Chart Illustrating Progress Across Priority Areas in Poland

3.1.7 Andalusia

Andalusia’s NOVAFERT action plan exhibits mixed levels of advancement, with a few actions already demonstrating tangible results, while many remain at early or conceptual stages. A major driver for progress is the Reclaimed Water Plan for Irrigation in Andalusia (plan PARRA), which channels significant funding, initially around €50 million, expanding up to €165 million to build pipelines, improve tertiary treatment plants, and ultimately connect reclaimed water supplies with irrigation communities (A7-A9, A15). Additionally, there is a growing emphasis on training and knowledge exchange via the Andalusian Environment and Water Agency (AMAYA), the Experimental Centre for New Water Technologies (CENTA), and IFAPA (Andalusian Institute for Agricultural, Fisheries, Food, and Organic Production Research and Training). These institutions facilitate awareness-raising events, demonstration workshops, and e-learning platforms (A19), laying a stronger foundation for future implementation of alternative fertilisers and reclaimed water solutions.

Under Legal Framework (A1-A2), efforts to align Andalusian rules with new EU and Spanish legislation on water reuse are partially underway. For example, Royal Decree 1085/2024 updates the legal framework for reclaiming and using wastewater, while the recast EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive extends environmental standards to smaller agglomerations and promotes stricter pollution controls. However, A1, A3, and A4 (e.g., forming irrigator associations, hiring specialised public staff, and strengthening coordination between national/regional administrations) have not yet progressed beyond initial conversations. The region also aims to increase transparency and oversight around reclaimed water (A5), although discussions with competent authorities remain at a formative stage.

In terms of Political Willingness, Andalusia has set long timeframes (2030 or beyond) for many institutional changes, such as hiring more specialised staff (A3) and driving inter-agency

coordination (A4). While formal petitions are not yet in place, there is general recognition of the need to unify efforts between the local government, irrigation communities, and national bodies like the Ministry for the Ecological Transition. A dedicated transparency portal (A5) could bolster public trust, provided data interoperability (A6) and real-time information on water quality are achieved.

Research & Technical Development actions (A6-A9) focus heavily on improving wastewater treatment infrastructure and ensuring that reclaimed water can reach fields effectively. Thanks to plan PARRA, several pipeline constructions (A7-A8) are already in progress in provinces like Málaga and Granada, with subsequent expansions planned for Almería and Jaén. Concurrently, the region recognises the need for storage infrastructures (A9) such as irrigation pools, although no specific projects have been finalised. Progress on New Business Models (A10) involves the use of digital twin technology to simulate water usage, ultimately aiming to reduce costs and scale up efficient irrigation practices. While this goal aligns with ongoing digitalisation efforts in plan PARRA, it is still in a preliminary phase, requiring clearer investment frameworks and user buy-in. Collaboration with local agritech companies and irrigation associations is identified as the next crucial step to make these pilots more robust.

Despite growing interest in alternative fertilisers and water-efficient irrigation, Financial Incentives (A11-A13) remain largely uninitiated. Establishing tax deductions (A11) or a joint venture capital fund (A12) to encourage technology uptake has not gone beyond conceptual discussions. Similarly, although local stakeholders recognise the potential synergy with EU strategies like “Farm to Fork,” no concrete subsidies or preferential financing have yet been formalised (A13). On Self-Sufficiency (A14-A15), early steps are underway to create an open digital platform (A14) that could use AI or at least advanced data analysis to tailor recommendations on fertiliser rates, based on real-time field data. A proto tool by BIOAZUL is already being developed to help farmers calculate fertilisation needs using reclaimed water. Additionally, infrastructure updates (A15) partially benefit from plan PARRA’s pipeline expansions, though more advanced integration of renewable energy or deeper hydrological studies will be needed to ensure stable, self-sufficient water supply across the region.

Public Acceptance efforts (A16–A19) range from broad advertising campaigns (A16) to targeted school outreach (A17), to setting up formal training centres (A19). The region has had some success in educational initiatives: a summer course at the International University of Andalusia (UNIA) and a master’s program in water resources at the University of Málaga (UMA) have introduced the concept of reclaimed water and circular economy to students. Additionally, the workshop on “Urban Water Cycle: Purification and Reuse” in April 2025 engaged more than 200 participants. However, no major public-facing campaign (A16) has started, nor has any official circularity certificate (A18) been created for verifying the resource efficiency of end-products. In the realm of Environmental Protection (A20), Andalusia is investigating emerging pollutants (e.g., pharmaceuticals, personal care products) through partnerships with universities in Málaga, Granada, and Cádiz. This effort remains in an early planning stage, but future discussions with research groups should identify key removal technologies and define minimum standards for safe reclaimed water usage.

Table 9; Overview of Progress Across Eight Priority Areas in Andalusia

Priority Area	Action	Progress Score	Comments
Legal Framework	A1. Regularisation of irrigation communities to improve efficiency and control of water use	1	Begin initial conversations with regional authorities to clarify legal pathways and encourage farmer associations.
Legal Framework	A2. Harmonisation of national and European legislation on water reuse	5	Align new Royal Decree 1085/2024 with local measures; clarify responsibilities for monitoring and enforcement.
Political Willingness	A3. Increase specialised staff in public administration	1	Draft a formal petition for increased hiring/training in public agencies responsible for water management and reclaimed water projects.
Political Willingness	A4. Coordination between national and regional administrations	1	Organize joint workshops or steering meetings to align national/regional agendas; submit a coordination proposal to authorities.
Political Willingness	A5. Foster a transparency portal to share reclamation processes, water quality data	1	Engage the Andalusian Environment and Water Agency (AMAYA) to determine how reclaimed water data might be integrated into the existing portal.
Research & Tech Dev.	A6. Facilitate data interoperability (common criteria/protocols for water quality, flows, etc.)	1	Define the parameters (e.g., contaminants, flow rates) to be displayed publicly; coordinate with AMAYA to standardize data collection.
Research & Tech Dev.	A7. Improve existing infrastructures (secondary & tertiary treatment) under "plan PARRA"	4	Identify new projects for Almería, Jaén, and potential expansions; ensure synergy with ongoing digitalisation plans.
Research & Tech Dev.	A8. Assure accessibility of reclaimed water to irrigable areas	3	Upcoming Period: Conduct feasibility studies in unserved areas; consult irrigation communities to finalize pipeline routes and collaboration.

Research & Tech Dev.	A9. Build reclaimed water storage infrastructures (irrigation pools)	3	Assess budget requirements, potential sites, and synergy with existing irrigation networks.
New Business Models	A10. Form user associations to share costs/scale sensing technology via digital twins	2	Map local agritech companies, finalise a pilot study on user associations and digital twins for efficient water use, incorporate them into future plan PARRA expansions.
Financial Incentives	A11. Establish incentives (tax deductions) for water saving using on-farm sensing technology	1	Develop a formal proposal outlining tax incentives; consult with relevant authorities and farmer groups on feasibility.
Financial Incentives	A12. Create a joint venture capital fund (sector fund)	1	Identify stakeholders (agriculture, financial institutions) willing to collaborate; draft a baseline framework to spur sector-focused financing.
Financial Incentives	A13. Offer economic incentives for using alternative fertilisers (grants, tax benefits, awareness campaigns)	1	Begin talks with regional administration about "Farm to Fork" strategies; design pilot awareness campaigns; specify any budget lines for direct or indirect subsidies.
Self-Sufficiency	A14. Develop an open digital platform (EU scope) with on-site data for personalised crop fertilisation advice	2	Refine the tool's accuracy, explore partial AI integration, and evaluate how to scale for EU-wide applicability.
Self-Sufficiency	A15. Update infrastructure (evaluate population growth, integrate renewables, improve distribution)	2	Study renewables integration; plan expansions beyond existing major projects to ensure regional coverage.
Public Acceptance	A16. Promote citizen participation (ad campaigns, prime-time outreach)	1	Seek institutional support (municipal/regional) to shape a formal media strategy; define target audiences, key messages, and spokespersons.
Public Acceptance	A17. Create communication campaigns for young students (schools, social media, influencers)	4	Expand youth-focused initiatives; leverage the Master's in Water Resources for broader training and real-world demonstrations.

Public Acceptance	A18. Design an official certificate on products' circularity	1	Identify expert commission to define criteria; clarify how to seek official recognition for such a certificate.
Public Acceptance	A19. Provide training & information for decision-makers (regional training centre, demos, open days)	4	Expand demonstration events focusing on reclaimed water for irrigation and alternative fertilisers; coordinate scheduling through existing training portals.
Environmental Protection	A20. Remove emerging/other pollutants from reclaimed water	2	Convene expert discussions to prioritise pollutants, identify effective removal technologies, and seek pilot funding.

Figure 7. Radar Chart Illustrating Progress Across Priority Areas in Andalusia

3.1.8 Key Insights from the NOVAFERT Action Plans

The NOVAFERT project showcases a wide variety of strategies, achievements, and remaining challenges across seven European regions, Flanders, Croatia, Finland, Ireland, Catalonia, Poland, and Andalusia, in their chase of more sustainable fertiliser use and nutrient management. While each region tailors its initiatives to local conditions, several cross-cutting themes emerge from this consolidated monitoring: the need for clear legislative frameworks, targeted financial incentives, strong stakeholder engagement, and practical demonstration of alternative fertilisers' benefits in real-world conditions.

3.1.8.1 Legislative and Policy Progress

Many regions are working actively to update or harmonise their laws so that producers and farmers can adopt alternative fertilisers without facing undue administrative hurdles. In Flanders, long-term visions for 2050 drive work on policy incentives and further dissemination efforts, while multi-stakeholder task forces ensure coordination across government, industry, and research. Although Flanders has made notable headway in scenario analysis, actions around drafting a Green Deal remain in conceptual stages, reflecting a broader pattern that finalising legal frameworks and forging political consensus can be time-intensive.

Croatia is pursuing similar goals by advocating for regulatory adjustments and learning from successful EU policies. The strategy here includes forming local partnerships and knowledge exchange campaigns to ensure new regulations align well with farmer realities. Despite clear policy intentions, many of these measures are still in mid-implementation, reflecting the need for additional resources and stakeholder input, especially for building up the local market for alternative fertilisers.

Meanwhile, Finland's main policy shifts are scheduled to begin more substantially in 2025. Collaboration with a fertiliser company is expected to advance manure-based products, but many actions like refining nutrient ratios and reducing logistical barriers depend on coordinating with various public and private entities. Although the legislative groundwork is laid, practical implementation hinges on robust testing and stakeholder buy-in in the coming years.

Ireland also focuses on legal alignment, ensuring compliance with European rules on alternative fertilisers, though it is still establishing incentives for adding soil carbon. Efforts to encourage nutrient exchange partnerships between livestock and tillage farms highlight how policy can foster farm-level collaboration. The real momentum comes from research at Teagasc and broad public awareness campaigns, yet fully linking these scientific insights with legislation, particularly for carbon credits and financing, remains a key challenge.

In Catalonia, robust legal and policy initiatives abound, from revising waste regulations to advocating recognition of RENURE products. Many proposals revolve around end-of-waste clarifications for organic materials, allowing these resources to be reclassified as marketable fertilisers. Although multiple dialogues with Spanish national ministries and the European Commission are in progress, some actions have made slower advances, indicating that industry stakeholders have not always identified them as top priorities. Nonetheless, Catalonia's drive to set targets and create a formal Nutrient Platform underscores its political willingness.

Poland exemplifies forward-looking policy work as well, reviewing regulations for manure, digestate, and sewage sludge and seeking stronger local authority engagement. Stakeholder sessions in Regional Working Groups have been effective for promoting environmental benefits and discussing new legislative approaches. However, actual legislative changes can still be slow, though momentum is enhanced by real-world pilot demonstrations and upcoming publications on best practices.

Finally, Andalusia's focus is mostly on water reclamation policy, given that the region's push toward reclaimed water for irrigation strongly intersects with fertiliser use. While official frameworks such as Royal Decree 1085/2024 modernise the rules for reclaimed water, actions on the ground, like forming irrigator associations and establishing a dedicated transparency portal, remain in early planning. Formal petitions for hiring specialised staff or creating new budget lines for advanced infrastructure are still under discussion.

3.1.8.2 Financial Incentives and Infrastructure

Across the board, financial support is crucial for accelerating adoption of alternative fertilisers, whether through grants, tax breaks, or venture capital funds. For instance, Flanders is exploring new schemes, although many are still in developmental stages. Ireland has identified economic support as a key enabler, and Poland's ongoing workshops aim to clarify available subsidies and grants for farmers. Croatia similarly seeks EU agricultural funds, emphasising the importance of cross-border partnerships.

Catalonia stands out for already having a structured incentive system that supports the construction of around 12 new medium-size by-product treatment plants per year. These state-backed investments make it easier to scale technologies that transform manure or other organic wastes into marketable fertilisers. Plans to extend incentives for sanitisation units highlight how an existing funding framework can expand to address additional technical barriers.

Beyond direct subsidies, regions are also improving infrastructure. Andalusia's "plan PARRA" invests millions in reclaimed water pipelines, showcasing how large public-sector projects can boost alternative fertiliser adoption by providing a stable water supply. Finland and Ireland similarly link their research outcomes with infrastructure development, though they are still refining cost-effective logistics strategies or investigating how best to align government grants with local production.

3.1.8.3 Research, Technical Development, and New Business Models

Research and innovation feature strongly in each region's plan, with demonstration sites, field trials, and knowledge transfers offering critical real-world data. Flanders continues to strengthen its position as a knowledge hub, hosting conferences like ManuREsource and ESNI to share findings on bio-based fertilisers. Croatia relies heavily on raising awareness, compiling comparative studies, and transferring regulatory best practices to local stakeholders. Finland's timeline sees major R&D actions starting in 2025, from testing new nutrient ratios to proving the environmental benefits of manure-based fertilisers. Ireland, similarly, invests in field experiments and demonstration farms through Teagasc, ensuring that scientific data inform both policy and farmer education. Catalonia uses public calls and demonstration-focused "Operative Groups" to explore different approaches, from anaerobic digestion and composting to more advanced processes that concentrate or refine nutrients. Shared infrastructure, market-driven synergy among waste producers, and advanced digital tools aim to create a strong circular bioeconomy. Poland has also identified R&D in waste-to-fertiliser technologies as a priority, showcasing pilot projects at "lighthouse" visits to encourage farmer uptake.

3.1.8.4 Stakeholder Engagement and Public Acceptance

All regions recognise that public buy-in, particularly from farmers, is critical to the success of alternative fertilisers. Flanders leverages the Nutricycle Vlaanderen platform, effectively reaching a broad audience via newsletters, events, and workshops. Ireland's demonstration farms have likewise drawn a range of participants, including local communities and policymakers.

In Croatia, multiple field days and social media campaigns highlight the environmental and economic advantages of bio-based alternatives, while public outreach in Poland includes a short educational movie set for release in 2025. Poland's workshops have drawn nearly 80 farmer participants, indicating a strong appetite for practical information on these new products. Finland is slightly behind in public outreach timing, but in 2025 it plans to intensify awareness-building around food safety and logistical feasibility.

Andalusia's approach aims at forging a culture of water reuse and reclaimed water usage, though many actions remain on the drawing board. Training opportunities through institutions like the Experimental Centre for New Water Technologies (CENTA) and IFAPA have begun to mobilise farmers, students, and other sector professionals. Catalonia also focuses on building social acceptance through demonstration events (C28) and digital platforms (BioHubCat), ensuring that farmers and communities see tangible results and connect with potential business partners.

3.1.8.5 Outlook

Collectively, the NOVAFERT regions are making considerable headway. Actions range from the fundamental, such as mapping local by-product streams or building new pipelines, to higher-level objectives like fostering carbon markets or simplifying end-of-waste rules. Despite differences in scope and timelines, the overarching themes are clear: each region needs well-structured legislation, accessible financial incentives, ongoing research, and strong stakeholder engagement.

Looking forward, maintaining momentum and coordination across ministries, industries, research bodies, and farming communities will be crucial. The next six months will likely see further alignment of economic incentives (e.g., Poland's and Ireland's planned workshops), deeper demonstration of field results (Flanders' and Ireland's ongoing trials), and additional efforts to simplify legal requirements (Catalonia's end-of-waste clarifications, Croatia's and Finland's regulatory efforts). By continuing to share knowledge, refine policy, and scale successful pilots, each region has the potential to significantly accelerate its shift toward resource-efficient, circular nutrient systems.

In conclusion, the NOVAFERT project has facilitated an impressive array of regional actions that collectively push Europe closer to sustainable fertiliser practices. While some initiatives are clearly well-established and delivering results, others need more time and coordination to reach maturity. Nonetheless, the combined efforts better legislation, financial incentives, dynamic research, and inclusive stakeholder engagement offer a promising blueprint for how the circular-nutrient economy can thrive on both local and broader scales.

3.2 Dash board indicators

In this section, we present the indicators and results for five distinct technologies involved in the production of alternative fertilisers. These technologies include Stripping & Scrubbing in Flanders, Thermal/Hydrothermal Conversion in Poland, Membrane-Based Technology in Catalonia, Mechanical Separation in Finland, and Desalination, Dewatering, and Granulation in Ireland. Each technology is assessed through a set of carefully selected performance indicators, focusing on critical aspects such as nutrient recovery rate, sustainability, market readiness, and agro-performance. The indicators are designed to provide insights into the operational efficiency, environmental impact, and market potential of each technology, thereby supporting informed decision-making and strategic planning in the development of biobased fertilization solutions.

3.2.1 Stripping and scrubbing (Flanders)

The Detricon Ammonia Mining Unit is a complete solution for reducing the ammonia load in wastewaters while at the same time producing a valuable ammonium salt solution. Ammonia can be extracted from all kinds of liquid streams such as digestate, manure, leachate, etc.

The product derived from this technology has a nutrient content with nitrogen (N-P-K %) of 18-0-0 or 8.5-0-0, and a pH of 7.0. The technology's nutrient recovery rate is 75%, and its nutrient use efficiency ranges between 113% and 142%. The composition of the fertilizer includes nitrogen content (N-P-K %) of 18-0-0 or 8.5-0-0 with a pH of 7.0. The product is classified with a PFC label (PFC1 C), indicating its role as an inorganic macronutrient fertilizer.

The technology has successfully completed all stages of development and fine-tuning, with suppliers now entering the market with full-scale solutions (TRL 8). However, market adoption has been slow, limiting the number of full-scale implementations. A procedure is in place to include this technology on the PAS-list for subsidisable emission reduction technologies, and it is awaiting the RENURE legislation to further support its growth in the agronomic sector (MRL 6). The technology has been tested in several European projects, including Digesmart, Nitroman, and Life INFUSION, demonstrating its effectiveness in improving crop health and nutrient recovery across different crops and regions (APRL 8). Sustainability has been a key focus in the ongoing development and testing of the "Stripping and Scrubbing" technology. Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) have been conducted in European projects, particularly in Life INFUSION, to evaluate the environmental impacts of the technology (SRL 6). The data collected from these projects supports the optimization of the technology and informs further research, ensuring that the technology not only meets agronomic standards but also aligns with broader environmental objectives. Ongoing work in these areas will continue to support its development and optimization, further improving its sustainability performance. technology is progressing well across all readiness levels, with significant advancements in its technology, market acceptance, agronomic performance, and sustainability. While there are challenges in terms of market adoption, the technology shows strong potential for widespread use in the future, particularly with the pending regulatory support and demonstrated agricultural benefits. With further optimization and testing in European projects, it is expected that the technology will gain further traction and contribute to sustainable farming practices and nutrient recovery solutions in the near future.

Figure 8. Dashboard Indicators for Stripping and Scrubbing Processes

3.2.2 Membrane based technology (Catalonia)

The Membrane-based Technology in Catalonia is designed to concentrate nutrients through a membrane filtration (MF) process, where 20-30% of the inlet nutrients are recovered in the concentrate. The nutrient use efficiency is expected to range between 20% to 70%, depending on several factors such as treatment, application, soil conditions, crop type, growth stage, and application method. The technology complies with the Fertilizing Products Regulation (FPR), specifically under categories identified in the FPR (2019/1009). It is classified with a PFC1 B label, indicating that it produces an organo-mineral macronutrient fertilizer when a concentration step is applied. The compositional parameters depend on the input material and membrane used, with nutrient content varying between 0.3-1.2% Nitrogen (N), 0.03-0.2% Phosphorus (P), and 0.2% Potassium (K). This fertilizer is typically used in fertigation or requires further concentration for transportation.

In terms of APRL, the technology is rated 9, reflecting its proven effectiveness in agronomic testing. However, the product, which is concentrated for fertigation, requires further concentration before use, meaning that its practicality in terms of large-scale application may be limited. Agronomic testing has consistently shown satisfactory results, but the application of the concentrate as a primary nutrient source requires significant volumes, which may not be feasible for widespread use. Lastly, the SRL is also rated 9, as extensive sustainability data is available. The technology, while

effective, requires high investment in automation and maintenance, especially in terms of membrane replacement. Energy and chemical consumption are notable considerations, though full-scale sustainability data for varying input materials have been made available, providing a strong foundation for its environmental credentials.

Figure 9. Dashboard Indicators for Membrane based technology

3.2.3 Thermal/ hydrothermal conversion (Poland)

The Thermal/Hydrothermal Conversion Technology in Poland is a highly efficient method for nutrient recovery, with a nutrient recovery rate of 100%. This technology processes sewage sludge into a soil improver, significantly reducing waste and emissions related to disposal. The conversion process ensures that the nutrients, particularly macro- and micronutrients, are effectively recovered and utilized. The product derived from this technology is classified as PFC 3- soil improver under the EU Fertilizing Products Regulation (2019/1009), and it contains a nutrient composition of N-P-K (kg/t): 38-39-50, along with more than 50% organic matter. This high nutrient content, combined with the organic matter, makes it an excellent soil improver, enhancing soil health and fertility when applied in agricultural practices.

The technology is fully compliant with the relevant EU regulations and has achieved significant progress in terms of both TRL (9) and MRL (9). Emission reductions are a key benefit of this system, as it mitigates environmental impact by processing sewage sludge rather than sending it to landfills or incineration, thus lowering greenhouse gas emissions and other pollutants. The technology's nutrient use efficiency is enhanced

by the presence of both macro- and micronutrients, making it an effective and sustainable option for soil improvement. With ongoing efforts to further optimize and scale the technology, it is well-positioned for broader market adoption, supporting both environmental sustainability and efficient agricultural practices.

Figure 10. Dashboard Indicators for Thermal/ hydrothermal conversion

3.2.4 Mechanical separation (Finland)

The Mechanical Separation Technology in Finland is designed to separate nitrogen- and phosphorus-rich fractions from anaerobically digested slurry, offering an effective solution for nutrient recovery. With a nutrient recovery rate of 70-80%, this technology has demonstrated significant potential for improving nutrient management in agriculture. The system has been implemented on a large pig production farm, where the liquid fraction is applied to surrounding fields, benefiting both crop productivity and soil health. The technology also uses an integrated application system, which reduces soil compaction during nutrient application, further enhancing soil quality. Currently, the Nutrient Use Efficiency will be determined during the trial in the next growing season, helping to refine the application of the recovered nutrients. In terms of TRL, the technology is at TRL-7, meaning it is in operational use and has been successfully demonstrated at a large scale. However, the technology does not yet have emission certification, and the reduction of emissions is still undetermined. The system is being actively promoted through market readiness efforts, including receiving nutrient recycling subsidies from the government, which incentivize the reallocation of phosphorus to phosphorus-deficient fields (MRL 6). Additionally, studies have

shown that digestate application improves the long-term carbon content of the soil, further enhancing soil health compared to conventional mineral nitrogen fertilisers. This technology is progressing well in terms of sustainability, with LCA assessments confirming that the climate impacts of the technology are lower than those of mineral nitrogen fertiliser production, making it a viable and sustainable option for nutrient recycling (SRL 7).

Figure 11. Dashboard Indicators for Mechanical separation

3.2.5 Desalination, dewatering, granulation (Ireland)

The Desalination, Dewatering, and Granulation Technology in Ireland, currently at a TRL-7, has shown significant promise in nutrient recovery, achieving a 36% nutrient recovery rate. The technology reduces the carbon footprint of the final product by 92-98%, compared to virgin products, making it a highly sustainable solution for nutrient management. Although the Nutrient Use Efficiency is currently under evaluation and expected to be below 99%, the product is already compliant with relevant FPR regulations (SI 248 1978 and EC regulation 2003/2003), indicating its alignment with European fertilization standards.

In terms of market (MRL 6) and agronomic performance (APRL 9), the technology is operational but has not yet been commissioned at a commercial scale. It has secured a market with a private company, though it is not yet available to the broader market. Agronomically, the product has been shown to have the same purity as commercial ammonium sulphate, which makes it suitable for use at large scales in agriculture.

Additionally, LCA assessments have confirmed that this process leads to significant environmental benefits, including carbon footprint reductions of up to 98% when using green electricity (SRL 9). This, combined with the product's effectiveness as a soil improver and the potential for large-scale deployment, positions it as a promising solution for sustainable nutrient management in agriculture.

Figure 12. Dashboard Indicators for Desalination, dewatering, granulation

3.2.6 Update and future use

Because the dashboard is intended as a living document, the values for the indicators can be updated whenever new updated data becomes available-whether from pilot studies, scaling efforts, or regulatory developments. This forward-looking approach ensures:

- Long-term relevance: The dashboard remains a go-to resource even after the NovaFert project concludes.
- Collaboration: Future projects can incorporate their data and build on existing insights, fostering continuity and collective learning.
- Policy alignment: As EU regulations evolve, the dashboard can be quickly updated to reflect new compliance requirements and standards.

More interestingly, the regional working groups and action plans established under the project can remain active and functional well beyond its conclusion. Since, most of these plans are designed for the long term, regional stakeholder engagement should

continue after the project ends. This creates a valuable opportunity to review and update the technology and product dashboard in light of the latest advancements in the field. Moreover, the same approach can be adapted to any future technology or product that emerges. Beyond this project, the dashboard itself can also be repurposed for other projects.

4. Conclusions

The NOVAFERT project has made significant progress in advancing alternative fertilization technologies across Europe, focusing on sustainable and circular solutions for nutrient recovery. The monitoring of the Regional Specific Action Plans has been a critical element in tracking NOVAFERT's progress. Through a structured and participatory approach, the project has successfully identified regional achievements, barriers, and key actions that drive progress across various European regions. This monitoring process provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of the RSAPs, ensuring that strategies are tailored to local conditions and helping to maintain momentum toward the project's broader goals. By continuously assessing and refining the action plans, NOVAFERT supports the alignment of regional efforts with its overarching objective of promoting sustainable fertilization practices and advancing nutrient recovery technologies.

From the above regional analysis on the progress of these action plans, certain actions have already been completed, while most are actively underway largely because of the longer timescales required to implement them. It is important to note that NOVAFERT has established a solid foundation for future initiatives by setting up Regional Working Groups and engaging the same regional stakeholders who participated in NOVAFERT. This continuity is expected to have a significant long-term impact, especially by aligning regional and national policies and raising farmers' awareness about the availability, benefits, and safety of alternative fertilizers.

The development of a dynamic and living dashboard further enhances the project's contribution by providing a real-time, user-friendly tool for tracking the progress of nutrient recovery technologies. By adopting a multi-dimensional approach to evaluating technologies, the project has developed a robust framework that includes Technology Readiness Levels (TRL), Market and Investment Readiness Levels (MRL), Agronomic Performance Readiness Levels (APRL), and Sustainability Readiness Levels (SRL). This comprehensive framework allows stakeholders to gain a detailed understanding of each technology's maturity, market potential, agronomic effectiveness, and environmental impact. The dashboard's adaptability ensures it will remain a relevant resource beyond the completion of the NOVAFERT project, offering continued value for stakeholders, policymakers, and future initiatives. The forward-looking nature of the dashboard, combined with regular updates based on pilot studies, scaling efforts, and regulatory advancements, will facilitate the ongoing dissemination of knowledge and foster collaborative efforts to accelerate the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices. As a result, NOVAFERT is positioned to play a crucial role in the transition to a circular economy in European agriculture, promoting

Novafert

the efficient use of resources, reducing waste, and enhancing the environmental sustainability of farming practices across the continent.

ANNEXES

Annex 1

Monitoring Progress of Regional Action Plans: example from Flanders

Action	What will we do?	Priority area	How will we do it?	When is it being proposed	1	2	3	4	5	6	Comments	Plans for next 6 months
B1	Incentive policy.	Legal Framework	1. Interdisciplinary collaboration. 2. Removing legal barriers. 3. Lead by example. 4. Research into related legislation. 5. Consultation with the Flemish entities.	Long term vision (by 2050).					X		Work in progress	Continue current activities
B2	Communication: translate national and international policy developments and research into the Flemish context and disseminate nutrient-related information.	Legal Framework	1. Nutricycle Vlaanderen Flemish consultation platform website, as well as social media, newsletters, trade press articles. 2. Nutricycle Vlaanderen Flemish consultation platform brochures.	4-monthly newsletter. 3 brochures per working year. 1 policy brief per year.						X	Main dissemination activities are through website and social media platforms and the organisations of events with partners	Set up a newsletter
B3	Establish a Multi-Stakeholder Task Force.	Political Willingness	1. Identify and invite key stakeholders. 2. Schedule regular meetings to discuss goals, challenges, and strategies. 3. Assign roles and responsibilities for advocacy and outreach efforts.	Already established, and further communications are ongoing.						X	A steering group meeting is held 3 times a year	Continuation of the steering group
B4	Flanders as a European knowledge region in the field of nutrient cycling and recovery	Research and technical development	1. Digital, regularly updated inventory of research on Nutricycle Flanders website. 2. Support of the broader RE-SOURCE.BIO and Biorefinery Cluster Europe network. 3. Connecting knowledge centres to further strengthen inter-university cooperation, including targeted workshops and webinars. 4. Analogous scientific cooperation framework in the field of R&D on the Nexus Nutrients-Water-Energy. 5. ManuResource biannual conference organisation. 6. European Sustainable Nutrient Initiative annual event organisation in Brussels. 7. Translation of international research into the Flemish language and context by Nutricycle Flanders.	1. Joint PhD, until 2029. 2. Scientific cooperation framework, ongoing efforts. 3. ManuResource, annually. 4. ESN conference, annually.						X	The website of Nutricycle Vlaanderen is kept up to date	
B5	Systemic scenario analysis for more sustainable nitrogen, phosphorus and protein flows in the food chain.	Research and technical development	1. Inventory of N and P flows in Flanders and identification of the junctions. 2. Development and application of a powerful and user-friendly model to map shifts in nutrient and protein flows in Flanders. 3. Recording and calculating indicators that estimate nutrient efficiency and circularity.	2023-2026.					X		Creation of a protein dashboard.	
B6	Foster Public-Private Partnerships.	Research and technical development	1. Identify potential private sector partners such as fertiliser companies and agritech startups. 2. Facilitate collaboration between public institutions and private companies. 3. Promote joint ventures and funding opportunities for R&D in biobased fertilisers.	frame of multiple EU projects.					X			
B7	Counter function for first-line advice	New business models	Providing a counter function (digital & contact person) that gives a complete picture of nutrient recovery in Flanders and works as a contact point for first-line advice.	2023-2026.						X	A general e-mail address is established and several questions have been answered or referred.	Keep following up incoming questions.
B8	Drawing up a Green Deal for the implementation of the Action Plan.	New business models	1. Catalysis and monitoring of the Green Deal by Nutricycle Flanders.	2023-2026.			X				Has been proposed during meeting but no concrete action yet.	Launch a new proposal to draft a green deal.
B9	Provision of economic incentives to farmers that use alternative fertilisers by public administration	Financial incentives	1. Awareness campaigns development to promote alternative fertilisers, contributing to the EU strategy "Farm to Fork". 2. Creation of a set of national, regional, and/or local taxes/bonification / exemptions. 3. Development of preferential financing options for alternative fertiliser infrastructure.	1-2 years.			X				Workagenda bioeconomie Vlaanderen Circulair	Continuation of the steering group
B10	Optimised manure management by closing cycles at company level, such as pocket fermentation or farm composting.	Self sufficiency	1. Monitoring nutrient management, including methane emissions from installed pocket digesters 2. Optimisation of nutrient use. 3. Experiences, networking, demo sessions, workshops further spread farm composting within the sector. 4. Support of local partnerships (legal framework, advice, analyses).	Ongoing effort					X		Supporting different projects (Boost, ChicoryREpowered...)	
B11	Stakeholder interaction through organisation's own workshops and support organisation of other actors to shape the transition from nutrient removal to nutrient recovery.	Public acceptance	1. Establishment of working groups. 2. Organisation of workshops in the context of NOVAFERT and other EU projects. 3. Working groups meetings. 4. Organisation of 2 thematic workshops per year.	Working groups already established in 2023. Organisation of 2 thematic workshops per year.						X	In 2024 we organised Living Lab in April, field visit in August, and planned Nutricycle event for January 2025	Continued organisation of workshops
B12	Providing information to farmers about RENURE products and new organo-mineral fertilisers, growth substrates and soil improvers that (under the new EU regulations) can replace products from primary raw materials in Flanders.	Public acceptance	1. Nutricycle Flanders will work on a series of target group-oriented documents. 2. Workshops / webinars and demonstration moments for farmers in the field will also be organised.	Already implemented as part of the NutriCycle project, to be expanded in the framework of continuing projects over the next three years.						X	Recurring topic through the workshops and events.	Project ReMestV (VCM & Inagro).
B13	Substantiating and supporting precision agriculture to achieve optimal coordination and allocation of raw materials based on local crop and soil needs.	Environmental protection	1. Setting up a centre for precision fertilisation in Flanders. 2. Developing technology for variable fertilisation with various types of fertilisers. 3. Specific soil management.	Ongoing effort.						X		
B14	Scientific research into agronomic and environmental performance of bio-based mineral nitrogen fertilisers (N) with specific attention to field validation.	Environmental protection	1. Monitoring nitrogen losses. 2. Monitoring the quality (variation in composition, stability) of the bio-based mineral N fertilisers. 3. Building up practical experience in real conditions (fertilisation regimes and methods, storage and transport).	Some of the analyses have already been done, but it will be ongoing effort within the framework of programs.						X		

Annex 2

Four-Dimensional Readiness Level Evaluation System

Technology Readiness Level		Reason for your score	Market and investment readiness level		Reason for your score	Agronomic Performance Readiness level		Reason for your score	Sustainability Readiness Level	
TRL			MRL			APRL			SRL	
Basic principles observed	1	Initial scientific research has identified, basic principles underlying the technology.	1	Early indications of interest in the market are recognized.	1	1	The product has not been tested in any agronomic conditions.	1	1	Environmental Impact Knowledge: not even minimal awareness of environmental
	2	Technology concept formulated, a specific application of the technology is proposed and planned.		Initial research into available governmental funding opportunities.						2
Invention and research	3	Practical applications can be defined/researched but are speculative, and no proof or detailed analysis that the technology will work.	2	No awareness of applicable regulations for biobased fertilizers.	2	2	Initial laboratory testing to evaluate nutrient release rates and determine how the fertilizer releases nutrients over time.	2	No sustainability awareness	Environmental Impact Knowledge: minimal awareness of environmental impacts, with no product-specific data
	4	Laboratory experiments validate the technology concept and expected outcomes.		Begin engagement with early adopters; conceptual discussions with potential customers						3
Proof of concept	5	Active R&D is initiated to develop the technology further. There is a first idea of end-user requirements/specifications and/or use cases	3	Determine eligibility for government programs, tax benefits, or subsidies. Basic understanding of existing regulations, but no formal compliance actions taken.	3	3	Controlled Pot Trials for Crop Response	3	Emerging awareness	Environmental Impact Knowledge: initial research on environmental impacts focuses on resource consumption and waste.
	6	Individual components or processes are tested in a lab setting for functionality.		Conduct surveys to understand needs and gather user feedback.						4
Bench scale Research	7	Test results give initial evidence indicating that the technology concept will work (i.e. initial validation)	4	Applications submitted for initial grants or seed funding; received small grants or credits.	4	4	Controlled Field Trials with Select Crops	4	Basic environmental data collection	Soil & Ecosystem Impact Early assessments of soil health, nutrient leaching, and initial ecosystem effects are carried out.
	8	Component validation in relevant environment, refinement of formulation based on pilot field results. More defined end-user requirements/specifications and/or use cases based on feedback from end users		Preliminary research on regulatory requirements including RENEUE compliance, EU Nitrates Directive, and Fertilising Products Regulation; initial identification of necessary permits and documentation.						5
Pilot scale	9	System prototype in operational environment, Operational prototype tested and adjusted for scale.	5	Collaborate with stakeholders for pilot customer testing.	5	5	Wider Trials in Different Environments	5	Preliminary sustainability assessment	Sustainability Metrics: general sustainability metrics, such as greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, are identified but
	10	the technology in a form that can be used to evaluate the technical and/or manufacturing feasibility or utility of the final product		Received grants or credits to support prototype development.						6
Large scale	11	The prototype is demonstrated with full functionality in real-world conditions	6	Draft key compliance documents (e.g., safety data sheets, environmental impact assessments); initial regulatory consultations, focusing on the EU Nitrates Directive and RENEUE criteria.	6	6	Performance Across Varied Soils and Crops	6	Preliminary sustainability assessment	Environmental Impact Knowledge: Conducts initial lifecycle assessments (LCAs) to estimate environmental impacts.
	12	Prototype near or at the complete technology has been shown to actually work in an operational environment		Conduct field trials or limited commercial releases with target customers; establish feedback mechanisms.						7
Demonstration in operational environment	13	The technology is proven functional, reliable, and qualified for production and use.	7	Submit initial compliance documents to regulatory authorities, including EU Nitrates Directive and RENEUE criteria requirements; gather and incorporate regulatory feedback.	7	7	Long-Term Field Performance Validated	7	Pilot sustainability validation	Soil & Ecosystem Impact: Begins assessing soil health, nutrient leaching, and initial ecosystem effects.
	14	Validated portfolio of technologies and providers available		Secure government support linked to milestones, with private investor interest emerging.						8
System completed and qualified	15	The technology is fully implemented and actively used in the intended market.	8	Consistent demand with positive feedback from market segments.	8	8	Product Efficacy Established Across Regions	8	Sustainability integration	LCA is complete with a minimum requirements and certified
	16	Partnerships with government bodies to promote the technology and products		Consistent field trials or limited commercial releases with target customers; establish feedback mechanisms.						9
Full-scale application and deployment	17	Product gains strong adoption across multiple endusers segments.	9	Significant private investment for commercial scale-up, possibly with tax incentives.	9	9	Consistent Results Under All Conditions	9	Sustainability optimisation	Environmental Impact Knowledge: Expands LCAs with field-based assessments and
	18	Comprehensive regulatory application, meeting EU Nitrates Directive and RENEUE criteria; documents reviewed by authorities		Comprehensive regulatory application, meeting EU Nitrates Directive and RENEUE criteria; documents reviewed by authorities						10
Full Commercialization (Broader Market)	19	Sustained interest and distribution channels established with large distributors.	10	Ongoing support such as grants, tax credits, or price support.	10	10	Broad Market Adoption	10	Full sustainability compliance	Environmental performance is reported transparently
	20	Product undergoes negotiations or additional requirements based on full regulatory review for compliance with EU directives and RENEUE criteria.		Established presence in key markets, strong end-user satisfaction. Government recognition and incentives due to product's sustainable and compliant profile. Full regulatory approval achieved, product complies with all relevant legislation and is market-ready.						11
Widespread Market Integration	21	Established presence in key markets, strong end-user satisfaction. Government recognition and incentives due to product's sustainable and compliant profile. Full regulatory approval achieved, product complies with all relevant legislation and is market-ready.	11	Established presence in key markets, strong end-user satisfaction. Government recognition and incentives due to product's sustainable and compliant profile. Full regulatory approval achieved, product complies with all relevant legislation and is market-ready.	11	11	Widespread Market Adoption	11	Excellent sustainability compliance	Biodiversity Impact: Conducts biodiversity assessments in field trial areas.
	22	Established presence in key markets, strong end-user satisfaction. Government recognition and incentives due to product's sustainable and compliant profile. Full regulatory approval achieved, product complies with all relevant legislation and is market-ready.		Established presence in key markets, strong end-user satisfaction. Government recognition and incentives due to product's sustainable and compliant profile. Full regulatory approval achieved, product complies with all relevant legislation and is market-ready.						12

